

THE EXTENT TO WHICH EFFECTIVE INTERVENTION PROGRAMS RESTORE HUMAN DIGNITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MOMBASA COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract:

Following the rapid increase of reports concerning the radicalization of Kenyan youths and indulging youths into terrorism propagators such as 'Al-Shabaab' in some parts of Kenya; has created a need to identify and disseminate effective intervention programs that will bar young people from being endured to participate in murderous activities against their fellow innocent Kenyans. However, the present curriculum does not adequately address the issue of radicalising our young people into religious extremism and preventing young generation from joining terrorism groups. Until then, however, little was known about the extent to which effective intervention programs would restore human dignity in learning institutions. The purpose of this Paper, therefore, was to determine the extent to which effective intervention programs would enhance human dignity among secondary school students in Mombasa County, Kenya. To achieve this purpose, the study sought to address the following objectives: to identify intervention programs being offered in schools and describe how these intervention programs are being taught in schools. This paper adopted qualitative design. The paper was carried out in Mombasa County secondary schools. The paper targeted 30 secondary schools, 30 principals and three form students. The paper used interview and observation checklists to collect data. The paper held face to face interview schedules with the principals. The qualitative data from interview schedules and observation checklists were analysed thematically and the findings were quoted directly in the text. The main findings were that: majority of the secondary schools offer the following

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intervention programs as a better way of fighting radicalization: a culture of peace making, sports, leisure, cultural activities, drama, music and art and dance. The paper also recommends that teachers should teach skills on how to encounter proactive situation, moral values and intellectual pillar, physical and mental fitness; and drills through theoretical and practical approaches.

Keywords: extent to which, effective intervention programs, restore human dignity, among secondary school students, Mombasa County, Kenya

Introduction

Cindy, Abraham, Karol and Diana (2003) revealed widespread of wilful neglect and youth ferocity produce a need to propagate efficient prevention strategies. They further contend that these youth problems demand effective interventions that might help the curriculum specialists to modify the current education program. The same comments are confirmed by Reyneke (2011) who also observed the persistence of youth violence, crimes and antisocial behaviour in schools are due to lack of appreciation values in schools. In addition, Reyneke (2011) further argued that lack of discipline and respect in learning institutions are increasing problems throughout the universe and laments that teachers and students are often the victims of intimidation, harassment and verbal physical assaults.

Obioha (2013) points out barriers facing human person currently in the society such as vilification to his personality which constitute attempts to address the issue of abuse to human dignity. According to him, the major problem in the contemporary society is the rate at which human life is being pulverized and human dignity degraded with reckless abandon, which is largely due to inadequate understanding of the human person. Moreover, he noted that human life is increasingly becoming capricious and constantly under threat of imminent extinction. He discussed that there is much frustration in the world today, coupled with wars, unending civil unrests and terrorist attacks in almost all over the world on daily bases, In addition, he contended that there are undeniable cases of abuse of fundamental human rights and constant violations of the dignity of man.

Bamidele (2014) contended that peace education would foster the development of man to live and work in dignity, participate in the development of peace and establish the ability to compromise and negotiate with one another. According to him, peace curriculum would produce assertive humankinds; who will individually and collectively be committed to autonomy of thoughts and action; eradicate the culture of

violence and develop sustainable peace and he further commented that peace education is contributing to a peaceful environment. Finally, he reiterated the essence of education, is to develop human potentialities and the self.

Sawe (2015) argued that the fact that educational institutions in Kenya are now enrolling centres for Al Shabaab is worrying! Numerous reports from police reveal that: Universities have become Al Shabaab feeder institutions, and some students are already on the terror group's payroll. Furthermore, he disclosed an incident where the police arrested a form three student from Mukumu Boys High School in Kakamega County and the boy confessed to be a member of Al Shabaab. The student named three other students in the school who were members of the militia group, and who had threatened to kill him if he reported them to the school authorities. The student further disclosed that he was recruited by Al Shabaab while he was a student at Jamhuri High School in Nairobi before he joined Mukumu Boys. In addition, he reiterated that radicalization of students in Kenya is now a reality. Finally, he concluded that the news that Al Shabaab has infiltrated learning institutions as it hunts for recruits; makes everybody in Kenya even more worried.

The prevailing student violence is confirmed by the recent international and national reports on school based violence that point out gloomy pictures. The report reveals that learners and teachers are transgressors and victims of this unacceptable behaviour. The report further argued that misbehaviour in schools often violets the right to dignity of victims and transgressors; these victims could either be the learners or teachers. Mabatuk (2015) revealed that people think of schools as safe havens back in the day. Currently, the situation is not the same, Kenyan citizens have begun to worry about strangers or estranged family members who might come to school to look for learners. The report also reveal worry from education fraternity about violence, especially after 67 boys died at a school in Machokos in Kenya, when their dormitory was set on fire in 2011 allegedly by two students. Then, later came the terrorist attack on Garissa University College students on April 1 this year, where more than 142 students lost their lives and others left with serious injuries. Because of these dangers, Kenyans are now recommending numerous measures on how to protect schools. Some schools have put in place safety measures like fences and inspection, while others are yet to decide. The right to dignity and restoration of justice in schools was then determined as possible solution to protect, promote, and resolve the right to dignity of victims and reduce misbehaviour in schools. However, until then, little was known about the effective intervention programs that would enhance human dignity among secondary school students. That is why, this paper determined the extent to which effective

intervention programs enhances human dignity among secondary students in Mombasa County, Kenya.

The Art of Literature Review

The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), (2009) introduced a culture of peace making in all learning institutions. The reason was to systematize an initiative for social inclusion and violence reduction in schools. The program consisted of: starting open school programme, utilising school spaces available on weekends, offering activities in the areas of sport, leisure, culture, digital inclusion and basic vocational training, this initiation could break the institutional isolation of schools and placing them at the heart of coordination with the community, the programme embodies union of the principles of a culture of peace fostering and conflict resolution through negotiation. The UNESCO's initiation programme aids in strengthening the concept of lifelong education, as well as eradicating poverty. It focuses on building a new school for the 21 first century- one which typifies "a school as a location". This means a school which truly contributes to the holistic and human development of its students and the community.

The UNESCO (2009)'s programme functions to help to transform schools into welcome spaces where there is a sense of belonging, where peace exchanges and meetings take place. The goal is that schools ought to incorporate youths' requests into the programme being offered in weekends, as well as their artistic and cultural expressions thus strengthening the participation of students in school activities. The programme has enhanced integration among all participants involved in the process and enables the discovery of new ways to relate, which can generate a feeling of belonging which is crucial to youth leadership. The intervention programs are also an alternative to the lack of access to cultural activities, reality in the outskirts of Brazilian cities, access to culture, art, sport, leisure and education allows youths to find ways other than violence to express themselves. Student's participation in workshops in the areas of drama, art and crafts, music and dance as well as in other play based activities, broadens horizons, strengthens self-esteem and can help learners discover a new feeling of belonging to their school and community.

Levine (2015) evaluated an after-school program initiated by a Catholic Diocese to meet the educational needs of learners attending urban catholic schools. The evaluation applied student interactions, analysed the helpful ways that students engaged with each other during the after-school programs and also the manner in which students exhibited the need for greater support. The after-school programs

included: staff-students, staff families connected with students in the after-school programs and their families experience. The focus on relationships emerged as an explicit connection to the context of catholic social teaching (CST) themes of core, solidarity and community within the after school program sites, how after the school programs meet the needs of children attending low performing and highly poverty catholic schools to build social justice mission.

Kincheloe and McLaren (2003) disclosed issues of power and justice in the society and how the issues of economy, race, class, gender, ideologies, discourses, education and religion could interact to construct a social system. The same views are confirmed by Roman and Baybado (2008) who noted that, those who strive for institutional change, work for systematic changes that would create more just institutions. Furthermore, Roman and Baybado (2008) observed that social institutions do not by themselves guarantee as an automatically the common good. However, Pontifical Council (2004) contends that people cannot rely on institutions such as schools to promote justice; simply because they are organized or supported by the church or the state. Instead, just institutions can only exist when individuals within the ethical or moral motivations are acting within them. The commitment represents a reliance on agency where individuals have the ability and the obligation to work for justice and peace.

Ritho (2015) reveals secondary schools in Nakuru County, Kenya which have introduced militarised programme aimed at equipping both students and teachers with survival tactics and skills in the face of an attack. Moreover, he observed that learners are taught outside classroom activities such as: sweating and panting in the scorching heat as they clear obstacles: crawl inside bunkers fashioned from empty drums and dodge poles erected on a field in a zigzag manner. This intervention programs inculcates life skills pertaining to personal fitness and interpersonal communication skills among the learners. The training manual includes students jumping over water obstacles, crawling inside three drums fused together, running through a zigzag structure, ascending a step up concrete block, then crawling inside another straight timber structure and finally jumping over a three-metre high concrete wall. The water trench is the starting point, and is about one metre deep, which trainers are expected to jump over and immediately crawl inside the drums fixed to the ground. The programme provides the students with both physical and mental skills in case of a threat, they can save themselves while in school and outside the world.

Njoroge (2015) noted that students are given an opportunity to compete among themselves by going through the five obstacles spread across a distance of 50 metres, with the obstacles positioned at intervals of 10 metres. It is not for the purpose that Al

Shabaab would attack, but the learners must always stay fit and ready to face and overcome any challenge that may present itself to them along the way. The reason of this programme is to produce all-rounded personalities who can perform well in the classroom and are ready to face any kind of challenge in life with ease. Furthermore, he argued that moving in a zigzag style will not allow the enemy to take easy aim at the student as he would be the victim. The training entails three pillars that include how to encounter a provocative situation, moral values and intellectual pillar. The training provide learners with both physical and mental fitness, the students often receive instructions from the teachers very fast and enable students to approach examinations with ease if they take this exercise seriously. Furthermore, he contends that students face a life-threatening challenge and the training would provide them with the requisite skills to escape by either jumping over a wall, fence or applying the leopard-crawling style unnoticed by the enemy. The programme enable students to remain alert in the classroom, have sharp eyes whenever they walk along busy streets and crowded places and are ready to tackle any kind of threat they face after leaving the school.

National Cohesion and Integration Commission (NCIC) as cited in Muchiri and Ochiel (2015) confirm that teachers are better placed to cushion students from extremism. According to (NCIC) the government should include teachers in the fight against youth radicalization and extremism. The commission argue that learners are vulnerable and prone to coercion to join terrorism, hence the need to pro-actively engage the learners while at school. The commission has rolled out Amani Clubs to spearhead peace and anti-radicalization messages in schools hoping to ward off negative influence on learners during their formative years. Speaking at Kangaru High School in Embu County during a training workshop on guidelines for Amani Clubs for principals and head-teachers; he asserts that (NCIC) commission's first approach is to reach out teachers and engage them due to their proximity to students, thus strengthening their capacity to identify behaviour change among students. Teachers can identify the onset of bad behaviour in students. By so doing, teachers are in a better position to initiate remedial action at an early stage and teachers should be in the forefront in fighting radicalization.

Statement of the Problem

Human life is increasingly becoming capricious and constantly under threat of imminent extinction. There is much frustration in the world today, coupled with wars and, unending civil unrests and terrorist attacks all over the universe on a daily basis, there are undeniable cases of abuse of fundamental human rights of the people and

constant violations of the dignity of man. Radicalization of learners is now a reality in Kenya and news that Al Shabaab has infiltrated educational institutions as it hunts for recruits and makes everybody in Kenya even more worried! The High prevalence of delinquency, youth violence and other youth problems create a need to identify and disseminate effective prevention strategies that might help curriculum specialists to innovate more effective programs to restore human dignity. However, the current curriculum does not adequately address the issue of fighting radicalising learners into extremism. Until then, however, little was known about the extent to which effective intervention programs restore human dignity among secondary school students in Mombasa County, Kenya.

The Purpose of this Paper

The purpose of this Paper, therefore, was to determine the extent to which effective intervention innovation would enhance human dignity among secondary school students in Mombasa County, Kenya. The research objectives were: to identify intervention programme that were being offered in schools and describe how those intervention programme were being taught in schools. The findings of the paper might be of importance to the following groups of people: principals might come up with effective intervention program measures in schools, provide national curriculum developers with better ways of implementing effective intervention programs and provide necessary knowledge and skills to teacher trainers concerning implementation of effective intervention programs for secondary schools.

Research Methodology

This paper mainly employed qualitative method as an inquiry process that helped this paper to seek and listen to informants so as to build a picture based on their ideas about the paper. The paper was conducted in secondary schools in Mombasa County because reports from the police officers reveal high radicalization of youths into terrorism gangs and religion extremism. The paper targeted 30 secondary schools, 30 principals and 1800 form three students. The paper sampled 180 form three students, 15 principals and 15 secondary schools. The paper held face to face interviews with 15 principals of the sampled secondary schools purposely selected to seek information on effective intervention programs that are taught students and how they are taught in schools. The paper also used observation checklists during the form three classroom instruction in

three secondary schools to ascertain the intervention programs taught learners and how they are taught in learning institutions.

The research instruments were pre-tested in two of the public secondary schools not included in the actual study. Piloting provided an opportunity to make necessary adjustments to instruments. Ambiguous statements were rephrased and unnecessary ones dropped to enhance the validity of the two research instruments. Piloting corrected the errors which were made in the research instruments before they were applied in the actual research. The content validity was enhanced by the use of triangulation of the two instruments which were compared and cross-checked with the responses from respondents on same issues in the two instruments. The reliability from interviews and observation checklists were tested through the application of triangulation of responses from the two instruments. A letter from the Ministry of Education was obtained to allow for data collection. The researcher made appointments with the principals of the sampled secondary schools to notify them of the permission to carry out a study in their schools. The researcher himself interviewed the five principals. The researcher himself observed the intervention program during classroom teaching instruction in form three classes in the three sampled secondary schools. The data collection procedure lasted for a period of two weeks. The Qualitative data from interview schedules and classroom observation schedules on effective intervention programs were analysed thematically and were quoted directly in text.

Findings and Discussions

Interview response yielded 100 percent response rate. This was attributed to the fact that the paper personally interviewed 30 secondary school principals and those who were not present; the paper made follow up visits with respondents. The paper sought principal respondents 'views regarding intervention programs being offered in secondary schools in Mombasa County. In an interview with the principal respondents on the intervention programs being offered in schools, two-thirds of the respondents agreed that majority of the secondary schools offer the following intervention programs as a better way of fighting radicalization: a culture of peace making, sports, leisure, cultural activities, drama, music and art and dance. The findings are in line with those of UNESCO (2009). The programs ensure students participate in workshops in the areas of drama, art and crafts, music and dance as well as in other play based activities, broadens horizons strengthens self-esteem and can help learners discover a new feeling of belonging to their school and community.

One third of the principal respondents interviewed mentioned a few secondary schools teach their learners ethical or moral motivations, survival tactics, skills, outside classroom activities such as: crawl inside bunkers, dodge poles and jumping over meter obstacles, crawling inside three drums fused together, running through a zigzag structure, an ascending a step by up concrete block, then crawling inside another straight timber structure and finally jumping over a three-meters high-concrete wall. The findings are in agreement with those of Ritho (2015). The programme provides the students with both physical and mental skills and in case of a threat, they can save themselves while in school and in outside world. Many of the principal respondents established that the availability of resources normally influence the nature of teaching and learning of skills fighting against radicalization of students into Al-Shabaab and extremism. Using an observation checklist during classroom teaching in form three, it was found that secondary schools teach students the following intervention programs: a culture of peace making, sports, leisure, cultural activities, drama, music and art, dance, ethical or moral motivations, survival tactics, skills, outside classroom activities that provide learners with requisite skills to escape by either jumping over, a wall, fence or applying the leopard-crawling style unnoticed by the enemy.

The paper sought principal respondents' perspectives concerning how these intervention programs are taught in secondary schools. In an interview with principal respondents on how these intervention programs are delivered in classrooms. Most of the principal respondents interviewed indicated that teaching and learning of these skills on how to encounter proactive situation, moral values and intellectual pillar, physical and mental fitness; and drills are purely theoretical. The findings are in line with National Cohesion and Integration Commission (NCIC) as cited in Muchiri and Ochiel (2015). Teachers can identify the onset of bad behaviour in students. By so doing, teachers are in a better position to initiate remedial action at an early stage and they should be in the forefront in fighting radicalization. This points out that the theoretical approach seems to be the most preferable strategy of teaching and learning of fighting radicalization of learners. Less than half of the principal respondents interviewed pointed out that the practical approach is the method of teaching and learning of skills to spearhead peace and anti-radicalization messages in schools hoping to ward off negative influence on students during their formative years.

A quarter of the principal respondents interviewed indicated that the central approach is to reach out and engage teachers due to their proximity to students, thus strengthening their capacity to identify behaviour change among students. Teachers can identify the onset of bad behaviour in students. By so doing, they are in a better position to initiate remedial action at an early stage and teachers are in the fore front in

fighting radicalization. Using an observation checklist during classroom teaching in form three, it was found that secondary schools teach students intervention programs such as: on how to encounter proactive situation, moral values and intellectual pillars, physical and mental fitness; and drills through theoretical. Teachers use theoretical methods because they lack teaching and learning facilities which enable them to apply practical strategies. The researcher noted that a few schools were using practical strategies as the approach of teaching and learning skills to spearhead peace and anti-radicalization of students into Al-Shabaab and religion extremism. The findings are in agreement with those of Njoroge (2015) who confirmed that the purpose of this programme is to produce all-rounded students who can excel in classrooms and are ready to face any kind of challenge in life with ease.

Conclusions and Recommendations

From the findings of this paper, it can be concluded that most of the secondary schools in Mombasa County are teaching intervention programs such as: a culture of peace making, sports, leisure, cultural activities, drama, music and art, dance, ethical or moral motivations, survival tactics, skills, outside classroom activities that provide learners with requisite skills to escape by either jumping over, a wall, fence or applying the leopard-crawling style unnoticed by the enemy. It can be concluded that teachers teach these skills on how to encounter proactive situation, moral values and intellectual pillar, physical and mental fitness; and drills are purely theoretical and that the theoretical approach seems to be the most preferable strategy of teaching and learning of fighting radicalization of learners and it can be concluded that practical approach is the method of teaching and learning of skills to spearhead peace and anti-radicalization messages in schools hoping to ward off negative influence on students during their formative years.

Based on these conclusions, the paper recommends that teachers should teach intervention programs such as; a culture of peace making, sports, leisure, cultural activities, drama, music and art, dance, ethical or moral motivations, survival tactics skills, outside classroom activities that provide students with requisite skills to escape dangerous situations. The paper also recommends that teachers ought to teach skills such as: on how to encounter proactive situation, moral values and intellectual pillar, physical and mental fitness; and drills through theoretical and practical approaches seem to be the most preferable strategies of fighting radicalization of learners. Finally this paper recommends that the government should include teachers in the war against students' radicalization and extremism as teachers can identify the onset of bad

behaviour in learners. By so doing, teachers are in a better position to initiate remedial action at an early stage; so teachers should be in the forefront in fighting radicalization.

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